

THE IMAGE OF THE SUN IN EPIC WORKS

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Abstract: This article discusses the artistic-aesthetic scope of the image of the sun, its true essence, and its role in the lives of the heroes of the work. The whole can be expressed in a single symbolic image, including in the image of the Sun we see the same artistry.

Key words: traditionalism, work of art, sun cult, nature, mountain, war, fortitude, celestial symbol, primitive period, time, spring.

The image of the sun has a very ancient history in terms of tradition, and it expresses various symbolic meanings from the point of view of the human psyche and era in fiction, folklore, folk crafts, age-old customs and traditions. "Historian L.I. Rempl found that in the art of ancient times, the cult of the sun and moon, day and night, light and darkness, heat and cold dualism, heavenly symbols such as the tree of life and the eternity of the universe take a leading place. Also, "Among the ancient Turks, there was a widespread custom of hanging a circular plate with the image of the sun above the door of the house. This custom was kept in the memory of our people for a long time, and later the custom of embroidering the sun symbol on the door itself was born. They say that the pattern representing the image of the sun protects this house from the evil eye. Even in prose works, the Sun is extensive in terms of imagery. As soon as we hear the word sun, first of all, the golden rays appear in our eyes and mind shines, rise red from the early morning, and the dew is like dew on the plants, but there is a miracle in the sky that is very far from us. It is no exaggeration to say that the sun is not only a miracle of nature, but also an image from the heart of the works of our poets and writers. As we mentioned above, in ancient times primitive people worshiped many things, natural phenomena, creatures. For them, the sun, fire, and water are sacred. They believed and obeyed the power of such natural miracles. Since ancient times, the sun has been glorified as a symbol of power, confidence, and pride. Even later, the sun served as time. People determined the clock based on the location of the sun. In this way, over time, our writers and poets began to write works in praise of it.

A work of art is a means of artistic communication. Fiction and art live in the form of a work of art. Various images and symbols are illuminated in these works. And we will dwell on the image of the sun. The image of the sun in O'lmas Umarbekov's work "Don't be quick Sun" gives a person new feelings. The work is very impressive and will not leave any reader indifferent. The main character of the work is a woman named Sanobar, who experiences severe difficulties. Sanobar lost his only son Bahram and grandson Ilhom. Her rampart a spouse who gave him her infinite love, but he did not turn out to be the person she thought he was, because of his cowardice and lack of pride, he abandoned his wife to the torture of his enemy, and indifferently waited for her to be saved. Sanobar could not bear this cruelty, abandoned her husband and raised her son alone. At that time, while the breath of war was wandering, Sanobar's son also went to war and died bravely. Sanobar continues to live with his daughter-in-law Risolat and grandson Ilhom. When his grandson grows up, he goes to the army. Sanobar is an elder in the neighborhood and does his work with justice. Unfortunately, the news brought by two soldiers suddenly sinks Sanobar. Her grandson dies fighting the invaders at the border. Hearing this news, Sanobar and her bride are deeply saddened. After all, their joy, dream and hope came from Ilhom. However, Sanobar is such a strong and tenacious woman that she will never give up. ... " I only regret one thing. Life is passing by. I still have a lot of work to do. Especially now. Now I have to work not only for myself, but also for my son and grandson. Every evening, looking at the setting sun, I want to stop it. Don't hurry , Let the sun shine a little more, let me finish my work! She is comparing the rising sun to time. If time waits for her for a while, she wants to earn money for her lovers who have left this world. At first glance, the sun looks like you can hold it in your hand, but it is very big. Time is also measured in the same way, after all, a person's life passes in a moment. Time does not keep anyone waiting! Sanobar does not think that she is unhappy, on the contrary, she constantly repeats that she is happy. True, she suffered all the bitterness of life. Grief, pain, death, evil followed her steps. But in the early morning, the Sun took on a blue face. She radiated strength, perseverance, hope for a new day, and patience with her bright rays. So Sanobar, realizing this, stood up again and told the Sun that she had not yet finished her work, and asked for some more time. In the work, the sun is depicted in the image of time, which is the biggest part of human life. In Luqman Bo'rikhon's work "The sun has not yet set", the image of the sun has been a symbol of infinite power, love and friendship. If we look at the essence of the work, we will see a clear proof of this. The play tells about

young wrestlers Norsoat and Davron, as well as a girl named Tanzila. Davron was the leader of the "Kengsoy Eagles" gang, which Norsoat joins and becomes close friends with Davron. The slogan of this gang is "The sun hasn't set yet!" They shout this slogan with their fists in the air. This was a sign of their true friendship and strength. In this village there was a man named Usta Abil, who had no children. He takes a donkey to sell and brings a little girl with him. Her name was Tanzila. Tanzila could not get used to a new family and would run away, only Norsoat would catch her. Norsoat and Davron were interested in wrestling. Because Davron's father was rich, he sent them to a remote village, in the heart of a mountain, in the heart of a peaceful nature, to be apprenticed to Absal, a famous wrestler. In order to test their strength, they participated in wrestling competitions held at weddings.

- The sun hasn't set yet! "But that night, for the first time, it was as if the sun had set." This sentence from the Norsoat language has a deep meaning. At first we said that the sun has become a symbol of strength and friendship. So why is it included? There was a fight that night. A famous sambo master from the city brought two of his students. Davron and Norsoat went with them. At first, Davron entered the circle, unfortunately, Davron was defeated by a wrestler from the city and left the circle. It is clear from this that their Sun, which they always say is our strength, has set at this time, because the Age has been defeated. But the sun had not fully set, after all, they had friendship. Norsoat ran after Davron, waited for Davron to come to his senses for a long time and went to him. He encouraged Davron. Together they shouted "The sun hasn't set yet!" with fists in the air, and the children from the "Kengsoy gang" joined them. You see what a beautiful meaning there is in the fact that this one Sun does not set. They will never let their sun, i.e. their power, go down and be defeated. They imagine their friendship, pride, affection, love, power in the image of the Sun. We talked about a girl named Tanzila above. Growing up friends, Norsoat fell in love with Tanzila, but when he saw Davron and Tanzila together, he felt bitter towards his friend. In fact, he does not speak properly for a long time because he is afraid of Davron. Later, Norsoat realizes that he suspected his friend in vain and that his friend will not betray him. After all, there is a holy motto, the sun, among them. At the end of the play, Norsoat and Davron leave for military service. Their friendship, love, and strength will last forever, like the Sun. In the story "Boychechak" from the "Season of the Sun" story collection, the Sun is expressed with a special freshness. The hero of the story, Lutfulla, loves his village, especially the first small garden that opened in the spring, so much so

that when the small garden opens, he leaves all his work and immediately goes to his village. His wife and children do not like the village at all, but Lutfulla describes the village in such a way that, in my opinion, anyone who hears it wants to go. "Hey... you don't appreciate it," said Lutfulla, coming out of his room to meet him, "Pox will die in 5C° cold and 5C° heat... It will come out as soon as it snows. If you look after a week, no... it will die." It is necessary to see it now... We will show it to the children. They will remember it.. " If we pay attention to these words of Lutfulla, after the silver winter, the first spring sun shines and the snow melts. The first spring sun not only breathes new life into people's hearts, but also gives life to plants. Without the sun, without its golden rays, no plant can grow. In the story, the emergence of the flower is represented by the first spring sun.

To sum up, when a writer writes a certain work, he writes in search of life and existence. The images that occupy his thoughts acquire a deep meaning at first glance. We have seen several views of the image of the Sun above. This natural wonder, the Sun, embodies such beautiful images in the works. During the works, we considered the symbolic expressions of the first shining sun and the sun setting between the clouds at the end of the day in the lives of the heroes of the work. The author of the work expresses the first sun as a symbolic sign of the beginning of a new life, draws the sunset with life lines and decorates it with artistic decoration.

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